

QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART X

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For pharmacological study against amoebiasis, iodo and chloro derivatives of 8-hydroxy-5:6:2':3'-pyridoquinoline have been synthesised.

The extensive use of "Chiniofon" and "Vioform" in chronic cases of amoebic dysentery indicates the importance of 8-hydroxy quinoline residue for chemotherapy in amoebiasis. In the search for an ideal amoebicide, it has been thought of considerable interest to synthesise a compound having a pyridine ring fused to 7-chloro- or 7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline residue and to study its efficacy in the treatment of amoebic dysentery. In this connection it should be mentioned that some harmol derivatives (that is, compounds having a fused pyridine—indole system) have been found to be active as amoebicidal agents *in vitro* (Pyman *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2010; 1931, 36; *Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 727; 1934, 28, 264; *Chem. & Ind.*, 1937, 56, 789).

It has been shown (Ghosh, Banerjee and Laskar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 354) that some hydroxyquinoline derivatives can be prepared directly from the corresponding nitro compounds by applying Skraup's reaction. By taking advantage of this observation, a mixture of 8-hydroxy-5:6:2':3'-pyridoquinoline (I) and 5-nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline has been obtained directly from 2:4-dinitrophenol by Skraup's method. The synthesis of the compounds (I) from 5-nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline by Skraup's reaction confirms its structure. On iodination with iodine monochloride or chlorination with chlorine gas, the corresponding 7-iodo- or 7-chloro-derivative (II, R=I or Cl) has been obtained, and is structurally related to "Chiniofon" or "Vioform."

By applying Skraup's reaction to 5-benzeneazo-8-hydroxyquinoline, Matsumura (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 3974) has obtained a mixture of quinoline and a compound to which the structure (I) has been assigned. A comparative study of the derivatives of our compound and those of Matsumura indicates their identity (*vide* experimental). The formation of (I) from the azo compound is now explained on the assumption that concentrated sulphuric acid acts as an oxidising agent towards 5-benzeneazo-8-hydroxyquinoline. Sulphuric acid is thus reduced to sulphurous acid which, in its turn, reduces the above azo derivative to 5-amino-8-hydroxyquinoline which then follows Skraup's reaction. This behaviour of concentrated sulphuric acid has been pointed out in connection with the explanation offered for the formation of hydroxyquinoline derivatives

directly from the corresponding nitro-compounds by Skraup's reaction (*cf.* Ghosh *et al*, *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

8-Hydroxy-5 : 6 : 2' : 3' -pyridoquinoline (I).—Glycerine (140 g.), made anhydrous by heating at 180° (thermometer in liquid) for 30 minutes, was mixed to a paste by shaking with well powdered 2 : 4-dinitrophenol (50 g.) to which pure, concentrated sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 60 g.) was added dropwise with shaking. The mixture was then heated under reflux on a sand-bath with occasional shaking, when a heavy dark liquid was obtained. As soon as the reaction commenced with frothing and evolution of fumes, the flask was removed from the sand-bath to avoid too vigorous a reaction. After the reaction had subsided, the mixture was heated under reflux on the sand-bath for 2 hours with frequent shaking. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and lumps were broken. Pure, concentrated sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 60 g.) was then added dropwise with shaking and the mixture was heated under reflux on the sand-bath for 4 hours more, the flask being removed from the sand-bath when the reaction tended to become vigorous.

Next day the dark mass was taken out of the flask and thoroughly triturated with sufficient quantity of warm water in a mortar. The mixture was filtered and the clear aqueous solution treated with sodium carbonate till distinctly alkaline. A solid was obtained; this was filtered and washed thoroughly with cold water. It was first crystallised from alcohol (charcoal). The crystalline solid was next triturated with cold 10% hydrochloric acid and the insoluble portion filtered. The clear filtrate was basified with sodium carbonate and the precipitate was filtered, washed with water and dried. It was extracted with ether and after removal of ether, the residue (compound I) was crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in cream-coloured, slender needles, m.p. 160°-61°, yield 6 g. (Found : C, 73.08; H, 4.49; N, 14.57. $C_{12}H_8ON_2$ requires C, 73.46; H, 4.08; N, 14.28 per cent). Matsumura (*loc. cit.*) records m.p. 157-8° for this compound. Its alcoholic solution gives a greenish blue colouration with ferric chloride. The *hydrochloride* was obtained as light yellow rectangular plates, m.p. 274-75°. The *picrate* obtained was thoroughly washed with acetone and was crystallised from a large quantity of alcohol in yellow, rectangular plates, m.p. 237° (decomp.). (Found : N, 16.54. Calc. for $C_{12}H_8ON_2$, $C_6H_3O_2N_3$: N, 16.47 per cent.). The *sulphate* was obtained as a light yellow crystalline powder, m.p. 273° (decomp.). Matsumura records m.p. 237° (decomp.) for the *picrate* and m.p. 273° (decomp.) for the *sulphate* of his compound. Moreover, the analytical figures of his *picrate* correspond with those of ours. These observations indicate that the above compound (I) is identical with that of Matsumura.

The product found insoluble after trituration with 10% hydrochloric acid, as described above, was washed with aqueous sodium carbonate solution and was finally crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 177-78°, yield 1 g. (Found : N, 14.62. Calc. for $C_6H_6O_2N_2$: N, 14.73 per cent). Its identity with 5-nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline was confirmed by a mixed m.p. with a genuine sample.

5-Nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline.—For the preparation of this compound, according to the method of Kostanecki (*Ber.*, 1921, 24, 154), 5-nitroso-8-hydroxyquinoline was treated with

well-cooled concentrated nitric acid (4 parts) and the solution was poured into cold water, when a yellow precipitate was obtained, which was filtered and washed with water. Although this compound (m.p. 177-78°) is sparingly soluble in water, it has been found to be the nitrate of 5-nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline, because, when treated with concentrated sulphuric acid, a vigorous reaction takes place with rise in temperature. When cooled and poured into water, a yellow solid was precipitated which was purified through its sodium salt. The solution of the sodium salt in warm water, on treatment with acetic acid, gave 5 : 7-dinitro-8-hydroxyquinoline, m.p. above 280° (Found : N, 18.11. $C_9H_6O_5N_2$, require N, 17.87 per cent).

When the above nitrate of 5-nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline was triturated with excess of caustic soda solution and the resulting sodium salt was dissolved in warm water and the aqueous solution acidified with acetic acid, a yellow solid was obtained which crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 177-78°. It was proved to be 5-nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline.

Skraup's reaction with 5-Nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline : Formation of Compound (I).—The method was the same as mentioned before. The product was crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) and finally from ether in cream-coloured, slender needles, m.p. 160-61°. (Found : N, 14.43. Calc. for $C_{12}H_8ON_2$: N, 14.28 per cent.). Its identity with compound (I) was confirmed by a mixed m.p. and also through its picrate.

7-Iodo-8-hydroxy-5 : 6 : 2' : 3' -pyridoquinoline (II, R=I)—To a warm alcoholic solution of compound (I; 1.7 g.) was added dropwise iodine monochloride (1.9 g.) dissolved in alcohol. Immediately a crystalline compound was precipitated. The mixture was heated on the water-bath at 50-55° for 15 minutes, cooled and then filtered. The solid was triturated with dilute aqueous sodium carbonate solution, filtered and washed with water and then thoroughly with warm alcohol. It is practically insoluble in boiling alcohol and was crystallised from a large quantity of glacial acetic acid in greyish yellow needles, m.p. 217-19° (red colouration), yield 2 g. (Found : I, 39.92. $C_{12}H_8ON_2I$ requires I, 39.44 per cent). When heated with concentrated sulphuric acid, it evolves copious vapour of iodine. When its chloroform solution is shaken with dilute nitric acid, the chloroform layer slowly turns deep violet and the nitric acid turns yellow.

7-Chloro-8-hydroxy-5 : 6 : 2' : 3' -pyridoquinoline (II, R=Cl)—The compound (I, 2 g.) was dissolved in dry chloroform and to the cooled solution dry chlorine gas was passed till saturated. A heavy precipitate was obtained, which was filtered and washed with chloroform and ether. The dried solid was treated with water, when a clear solution was obtained which soon deposited a solid. It was filtered, washed with water and was found to be a hydrochloride, m.p. 147-49°. It was well powdered and triturated with concentrated aqueous sodium carbonate solution. A yellowish solid was obtained which was crystallised from alcohol in yellowish rectangular plates, m.p. 253-55°. (Found : Cl, 14.82. $C_{12}H_8ON_2Cl$ requires Cl, 15.40 per cent).

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